

Using FLOSS Project Governance to Support Project Activity

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Free/libre and open source software (FLOSS) projects often rely on governance systems that help organize the work of contributors. However, because such systems are also viewed as indicators of well-kept software, many projects only adopt them for the sake of appearances. How can project governance meaningfully support project goals and sustainability? To answer this question, we evaluate prior research and analyze README and CONTRIBUTING files from a large sample of FLOSS projects. The results suggest several ways that projects can and do develop governance.

FLOSS governance recommendations

FLOSS projects deploy a variety of strategies to manage contributions from both new and existing contributors, but which ones do they choose and when do they adopt them? Influential organizations like GitHub and Mozilla provide best-practice recommendations for projects to follow. This advice often focuses on the establishment of contribution guides, codes of conduct, and other project documentation early on in a project's lifecycle. Such recommendations reflect evidence that prospective contributors see documentation as an signal of organizational quality when selecting projects to contribute to [1]. Nevertheless, the implementation of governance documentation often runs into at least two issues: contributors end up enacting governance as hollow performance or publish documentation that is inconsistent with project practices.

1.

Governance as performance

Ubiquitous recommendations that project adopt governance documentation has led many of these files to become a perfunctory display. For example, we found that many first-version README and CONTRIBUTING files are published with little content, and often with none at all [2]. Why bother? If people treat governance documents as signs of project legitimacy or maturity, then projects will publish them lest they be perceived as illegitimate or immature. Publishing a document becomes an end in itself. The existence of a document no longer indicates the quality people were seeking: substantive engagement among project stakeholders to develop meaningful, intentional governance mechanisms to organize future project activity. Instead, the prevalence of negligible or empty documentation files suggests a widespread pattern of creating documents for their own sake.

2.

Inconsistency with practice

Even when documentation is intentionally developed, it may not be practical or reflect how things really get done. For example, many CONTRIBUTING documents neither provide useful information for newcomers [3] nor reflect the actual procedures for contributing to the project purportedly being described [4]. Such patterns illustrate how gaps between project practices and documentation can undermine the utility of the documentation for those it is theoretically designed to support. Often, root causes of these inconsistencies include lack of capacity among project contributors or lack of buy-in from contributors and maintainers—those tasked with monitoring and adhering to the routines specified in writing.

Community Guidelines and Recommendations

Creating useful project governance documents and systems requires intentional, community-led effort. While research in this area does not support specific, universal best practices, we offer several general recommendations for FLOSS projects developing and maintaining documentation:

- Resist the pressure to create governance and documentation solely to satisfy community checklists or guidelines. Empty files are neither useful for contributors, nor for projects, and may lead to wasted effort and hollow forms of “Potemkin” governance.
- Develop project governance through project-wide discussion and deliberation. Some case studies have found that documented governance may structure project activity more effectively if it has emerged from community-members’ conversations and desires [5].
- Regularly update governance to meet the demands of current project contexts. Different projects at different stages may require different kinds of procedures and rules. What works in the lead up to a first-major release may not work for the project as it grapples with long-term maintenance. One size does not fit all.

Plot of the density of the word count of the first versions (at one-week old) of README (red) and CONTRIBUTING (blue) files from a sample of projects drawn from the Debian package management system [2]. The x-axis represents word count and the y-axis represents the proportion documents. Overall, this includes README files from 4226 projects and CONTRIBUTING files from 714 projects. In both types of documentation, the first-version files are often very short (<200 words) with hardly any content. The median time that it would take to read a first-version README file from this data set is about 15 seconds.

References

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